

Method optimization for a simultaneous determination of neonicotinoid, carbamate/thiocarbamate, triazole, organophosphate and pyrethroid pesticides and their metabolites in urine using UPLC-MS/MS

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ABSTRACT

An accurate and sensitive method for the determination of a total of 23 pesticides and their metabolites in human urine has been optimised. The methodology is based on a previously published method based on solid-phase extraction with methanol and acetone followed by ultra-performance liquid chromatography coupled to tandem mass spectrometry (UPLC-MS/MS) in the selected reaction mode (SRM) with both positive and negative electrospray ionization (ESI+/-). The detection settings of the previous method, which allowed to determine the metabolites from 6 organophosphate and 2 pyrethroid pesticides, were optimised in order to include further pesticide groups, such as 11 neonicotinoids, 3 carbamates/thiocarbamates and 2 triazoles. The 5-windows method enduring 22 min was optimized with acceptable results in relation to accuracy (recoveries >75 %), precision (coefficients of variation <26 %) and linearity ($R^2 > 0.9915$). The limits of detection ranged between 0.012 ng/mL and 0.058 ng/mL. Samples from the German External Quality Assessment Scheme (G-EQUAS) encompassing 2 pyrethroids, 2 organophosphate and one neonicotinoid (6-chloronicotinic acid, a common metabolite of imidacloprid and acetamiprid) were analysed, and the latter, included in this newest optimization, provided good reference results. The method is optimal as a human biomonitoring tool for health risk assessment in large population surveys.

1. Introduction

Pesticides are ubiquitous pollutants of anthropogenic origin that are used in a large number of human activities, such as agriculture and gardening, as well as in daily life applications, such as to kill and repel insects, as creams and lotions for pest control, including in companion animals, among many other uses [1–4]. Once humans are exposed (by inhalation, ingestion and/or dermal contact), these xenobiotics are absorbed, usually metabolised by the liver and then excreted via urine [5–7]. Pesticides can be excreted either in their original form, or metabolised by conjugation enzymes into specific/non-specific metabolites [8–11]. Because pesticides are not selective enough, they are also harmful to humans [12]. Pesticides such as carbamates/thiocarbamates (CBMs), neonicotinoids (NEOs), organophosphates (OPs) and pyrethroids (PYRs) are neurotoxic compounds that mimic neurotransmitters, block specific receptors or alter the normal function of neuronal membrane channels leading to erroneous nerve signal transduction [4,

13–15]. Alternatively, triazoles (TRs) may disrupt all stages of hormonal function of the reproductive system causing hormonal imbalance and male and female infertility [16–18].

Target and suspect screening methods applied to human urine samples can provide a chemical characterization of pollutants such as pesticides, giving an idea of human exposures [19]. Suspect screening methods generate semi-quantitative data for a better compound prioritisation for further development of target-compound methods [3]. Thus, target methods based on liquid chromatography (LC) or gas chromatography (GC) are well-known for their ability to determine and quantify different sorts of pollutants of interest with a high sensibility and selectivity [20]. In addition, target methods have been used for routine analysis in human biomonitoring (HBM) studies, traditionally studying one or two categories of compounds, such as organophosphates and pyrethroids [19]. Le Grand et al. [21], Cequier et al. [8], Fernández et al. [22], and López-García et al. [23] developed different methodologies encompassing the detection of pyrethroid, organophosphate and

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Table 1

List of pesticides and their metabolites and instrumental analytical data of the analytes considered in the present study.

Parent Pesticide	Analyte	Acronym	Q-SRM	C-SRM	IR	CE ^a	CV ^a	RT	MRMw
Neonicotinoids (NEOs)									
Imidacloprid	Imidacloprid	IMI	256–175	256–209	1.1	20	20	4.53	2 (ESI+)
	5-hydroxy-imidacloprid	5OH-IMI	272–225	272–191	1.1	20	20	4.06	2 (ESI+)
	Imidacloprid-olefin	IMI-OL	254–207	254–81	9.9	30	10	3.86	4 (ESI-)
	6-chloronicotinic acid ^b	6CINA	158–122	158–78	1.8	20	30	4.33	2 (ESI+)
Clothianidin	Clothianidin	CLO	250–169	250–132	0.69	20	10	4.36	2 (ESI+)
	Clothianidin-desmethyl	DM-CLO	236–132	236–155	1.6	10	20	4.08	2 (ESI+)
Dinotefuran	Dinotefuran	DIN	203–129	203–113	1.6	20	10	2.87	1 (ESI+)
	Dinotefuran-desmethyl	DM-DIN	189–99	189–100	1.9	20	10	2.41	1 (ESI+)
Thiamethoxam	Thiamethoxam-desmethyl	DM-THX	278–197	278–167	1.9	30	10	4.79	2 (ESI+)
Acetamiprid	Acetamiprid	ACP	223–126	223–56	4.7	20	30	8.37	2 (ESI+)
	N-(6-Chloro-3-pyridylmethyl)-N'-cyano-acetamidine	NDM-ACP	209–126	209–90	5.3	20	25	7.57	2 (ESI+)
Carbamates/Thiocarbamates (CBMs/TCBMs)									
Carbofuran	Carbofuran	CARBO	222–165	222–123	1.2	10	30	10.31	2 (ESI+)
	3-Hydroxycarbofuran	3OH-CARBO	238–181	238–163	3.4	10	25	7.48	2 (ESI+)
Captan	cis-1,2,3,6-Tetrahydrophthalimide	THPI	152–81	152–79	5.8	20	10	6.02	1 (ESI+)
Triazoles (TRs)									
Tebuconazole	Tebuconazole	TEB	308–70	308–125	15.3	20	20	16.17	3 (ESI+)
	4-Hydroxy-4-(1H-1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethyl)-5,5-dimethyl-hexanoic acid	OH-TEB	324–70	324–125	4.2	30	20	11.69	3 (ESI+)
Organophosphates (OPs)									
Pirimiphos	2-diethylamino-6-methyl pyrimidin-4-ol	DEAMPY	182–154	182–84	1.3	20	40	4.65	1 (ESI+)
Diazinon	2-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-pyrimidol	IMPY	153–84	153–70	1.9	20	40	5.05	1 (ESI+)
Parathion	4-nitrophenol	PNP	138–108	138–92	8.2	20	45	8.66	4 (ESI-)
Chlorpyrifos	3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol	TCPY	196–196	198–198	1.0	7	10	11.28	4 (ESI-)
Coumaphos	3-chloro-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin	CMHC	209–145	209–117	3.2	25	20	9.70	4 (ESI-)
Pyrethroids (PYRs)									
Several PYR	3-phenoxybenzoic acid	3PBA	213–93	213–169	1.6	20	30	12.87	5 (ESI-)
Cyfluthrin	4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid	4F3PBA	231–187	231–93	1.3	15	25	13.04	5 (ESI-)

Q-SRM: Quantification Selected Reaction Monitoring; C-SRM: Confirmation Selected Reaction Monitoring; IR: Ion ratio; CE: Collision energy; CV: Cone voltage; RT: Retention time; MRMw: MRM window.

^a CEs and CVs refer always to the Q-SRM.

^b 6CINA is a common metabolite of several neonicotinoid pesticides, including not only imidacloprid but also acetamiprid.

neonicotinoid pesticides in urine, respectively. However, there is an increasing interest in multitarget methods, including the characterization of several types of pesticides in a single methodology [2,6,24]. Specifically, the method developed by Garí et al. [6], encompassing the analysis of organophosphate and pyrethroid pesticides, has been used since then for several environmental health studies, including European birth cohorts from Spain, Italy, Slovenia, Finland and Poland [5,25,26], as well as occupational studies in Spain and Argentina [27,28].

The current study has optimized a previously developed methodology with the aim of including up to 23 pesticides and their metabolites from five different families, including NEOs (11 compounds), CBMs/TCBMs (3 compounds), TRs (2 compounds), OPs (5 compounds) and PYRs (2 compounds). Some of the pesticides included in the method are still in use, such as acetamiprid (ACE), captan, tebuconazole (TEB), pirimiphos-methyl and several pyrethroids. Many others, however, have been already banned by the European Commission (No 1107/2009 EC, Table S1, Supporting Online Material), although traces of them are occasionally found in human tissues and fluids.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Standards, solvents and reagents

Analytical standards of pesticides and their metabolites were purchased as follows: Neonicotinoids such as clothianidin (CLO), dinotefuran (DIN), imidacloprid (IMI) and metabolites including dinotefuran-desmethyl (DM-DIN), 6-chloronicotinic acid (6CINA), imidacloprid-olefin (IMI-OL), thiamethoxam-desmethyl (DM-THX) and N-(6-chloro-3-pyridylmethyl)-N'-cyano-acetamidine (NDM-ACP), carbofuran (CARBO), tebuconazole (TEB) and their main metabolites, 3-hydroxycarbofuran (3OH-CARBO) and 4-hydroxy-4-(1H-1,2,4-triazole-1-ylmethyl)-5,5-dimethyl-hexanoic acid (OH-TEB), respectively, as well as cis-1,2,3,6-tetrahydrophthalimide (THPI), 3-phenoxybenzoic acid (3PBA), 4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid (4F3PBA) and 2-diethylamino-

6-methyl pyrimidin-4-ol (DEAMPY) were purchased from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany). Acetamiprid (ACP), clothianidin-desmethyl (DM-CLO) and 5-hydroxy-imidacloprid (5OH-IMI) were purchased from Camdridge Isotope Laboratories (Andover, MA, USA), 4-nitrophenol (PNP) from Supelco (Madrid, Spain), 3-chloro-4-methyl-7-hydroxycoumarin (CMHC) from Acros Organics (Geel, Belgium), 2-isopropyl-6-methyl-4-pyrimidol (IMPY) and 3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPY) from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).

Isotopically-labelled standards of 3PBA, IMPY, PNP, IMI, IMI-OL, CLO, DM-CLO, DIN, ACP and NDM-ACP were purchased from Cambridge Isotope Laboratories (Andover, MA, USA), CARBO and TEB from Dr. Ehrenstorfer (Augsburg, Germany) and THPI from TRC (Toronto, Canada).

Acetonitrile was from Panreac (Barcelona, Spain), methanol, acetone and water for HPLC were from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany). Glacial acetic acid was from Scharlab (Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain). All solvents used were of analytical grade. Finally, synthetic urine (Surine, Preserve Free), sodium acetate anhydrous and β -glucuronidase type H-1 from *Helix pomatia* were from Sigma-Aldrich (Madrid, Spain).

2.2. Sample preparation and instrumentation

The sample preparation and extraction procedure followed the method described by Garí et al. [6], using 1 mL of sample, 25 μ L of the available isotopically-labelled internal standards and a β -glucuronidase type H-1 solution (750 μ L) from *Helix pomatia* (specific activity of \sim 500 units/mg). Samples were incubated at 37 °C overnight and extracted afterwards using solid-phase extraction (SPE) cartridges (Oasis HLB 3 cm³, Waters, Milford, MA, USA). 10 μ L of a chromatographic vial containing a total volume of 120 μ L (MeOH:H₂O, 1:3 v/v) was injected into an Ultra-Performance Liquid Chromatographer (UPLC Acquity H-class, Waters, Milford, MA, USA) coupled to a Triple Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (XEVO-TQ-S, Waters, Milford, MA, USA) equipped with an electrospray ionisation (ESI) interface. The chromatographic separation

Fig. 1. Matrix effects percentages (%) for each target compound. Values close to 100 % refer to low matrix effects, while values higher or lower than 100 % indicate signal enhancement and signal suppression, respectively.

of the target compounds followed the method proposed by Garí et al. [6], with minor modifications. Specifically, the elution gradient consisted of a mobile-phase of acetonitrile and a mixture of HPLC grade water with 5 % methanol and 1 % CH₃COOH. The gradient started with ACN/mixture 2:98, increased to 20:80 in 4 min, then to 40:60 in another 3 min, to 50:50 at minute 14, and finished with 100 % ACN at minute 16.5. During the following 3 min the column was cleaned with 100 % ACN and adjusted to the initial conditions in minute 19.5 till minute 22. During the running time, the MS acquisition parameters changed following 5 distinct timed segments. In segments 1 to 3, data were acquired in positive ionisation mode (1st segment started at minute 2.5, 2nd at minute 6 and 3rd at minute 11, until minute 7, 11.5 and 22). Contrary, in segments 4 to 5, data were acquired in negative ionisation mode (4th segment started at minute 4.5 until minute 15, and 5th, at minute 11 until minute 22). The total run time was 22 min.

2.3. Quality assurance procedure

Data acquisition, data handling, chromatograms and instrumental control were performed with Masslynx software version 4.1 from Waters Inc. Data analysis (calculation of limits of detection, linearity of calibration curves, recoveries, intra-day and inter-day precision) was performed using the statistical software R [29].

Synthetic urine (Surine, Preserve Free, Sigma-Aldrich) was used for blanks, Quality Control (QC) materials and calibration curves. Two QCs were prepared at high (QCH) and low (QCL) concentrations, by adding 100 μ L and 10 μ L, respectively, of 1 ppm standard solution into a 10 mL sample of synthetic urine. Afterwards, 1 mL of the respective QC preparation was taken to include a QCH and a QCL analysis at each batch. Calibration curves were prepared by adding 25 μ L of different standard solutions containing the compounds described in Table 1 at different concentrations ranging from 2.5 ppb to 560 ppb into 1 mL of synthetic urine, yielding final concentrations of 0.06, 0.12, 0.24, 0.48, 0.95, 1.9, 2.4, 4.8, 9.5 and 13.3 ng/mL in urine. A batch included 10 calibration points, 3 blanks, 6 QCLs/QCHs, and up to 50 urine samples. Recoveries (in percentage, %) were calculated for each target analyte, based on spiked matrix concentration in relation to the synthetic matrix standard concentration, using QCH/QCL quantified with the calibration curves. We also confirmed that extraction recoveries between real (pooled) urine samples and synthetic urine samples were both within a 20 % range (data not shown).

Intra-day precision (coefficient of variation (CV), %) was evaluated by ten duplicate analyses of spiked QCL and QCHs. Duplicate analyses of spiked QCL and QCHs were performed in seven different days to obtain the inter-day precision (CV, %). The acceptance criteria for recovery and

Table 2

Limits of detection, calibration curve linearity, recoveries, intra-day and inter-day precision for the studied analytes.

Analyte ^a	LD (ng/ mL)	Linearity (R ²)	Recovery (%)	Intra-day precision (CV, %)		Inter-day precision (CV, %)	
				QCL	QCH	QCL	QCH
IMI	0.029	0.9983	98 (\pm 15)	14	14	15	13
5OH-IMI	0.035	0.9987	86 (\pm 11)	15	12	13	13
IMI-OL	0.041	0.9926	82 (\pm 13)	8	14	18	10
6CINA	0.022	0.9957	91 (\pm 28)	7.7	12	16	9.7
CLO	0.018	0.9982	99 (\pm 14)	12	13	18	15
DM-CLO	0.012	0.9999	95 (\pm 8.9)	6.0	7.7	6.3	7.3
DIN	0.017	0.9969	87 (\pm 16)	9.1	10	17	14
DM-DIN	0.023	0.9970	83 (\pm 26)	13	8.5	18	21
DM-THX	0.026	0.9995	95 (\pm 12)	11	10	11	15
ACP	0.017	0.9988	83 (\pm 14)	7.4	9.6	10	15
NDM-ACP	0.037	0.9994	78 (\pm 14)	8.8	8.6	7.7	14
CARBO	0.013	0.9967	97 (\pm 10)	8.4	7.8	10	8.8
3OH-CARBO	0.017	0.9953	90 (\pm 7.5)	16	18	23	16
THPI	0.048	0.9966	97 (\pm 24)	16	20	18	25
TEB	0.019	0.9969	96 (\pm 16)	5.3	9.7	11	19
OH-TEB	0.032	0.9988	93 (\pm 25)	9.1	25	18	26
DEAMPY	0.045	0.9984	86 (\pm 9.1)	6.6	2.2	6.5	5.3
IMPY	0.030	0.9961	92 (\pm 7.1)	6.2	1.0	6.9	6.3
PNP	0.058	0.9944	92 (\pm 23)	7.8	4.8	11	6.3
TCPY	0.054	0.9976	81 (\pm 26)	14	21	22	12
CMHC	0.039	0.9915	98 (\pm 21)	11	18	24	7.7
3PBA	0.041	0.9983	90 (\pm 26)	14	4.1	11	9.7
4F3PBA	0.052	0.9941	99 (\pm 12)	13	3.1	13	9.9

^a Acronyms in Table 1.

LD: Limit of detection; CV: Coefficients of variation; QCL: Quality Control Low concentration (\sim 0.75 ng/mL); QCH: Quality Control High concentration (\sim 7.5 ng/mL).

precision are 75 % and 25 %, respectively.

Matrix effects of the method were calculated using real (pooled) urine samples and synthetic urine samples, both fortified after the extraction procedure, according to Panuwet et al. [30]. The extract areas were adjusted using a logarithmic transformation to avoid compound-specific sensibility from the HPLC-MS/MS detection. Most of the compounds showed up to 30 % of signal suppression (Fig. 1). Only one compound (IMI-OLE) showed a signal suppression of 50 %, and three compounds, namely THPI, DIN and ND-ACP, showed a minor signal enhancement ($<$ 110 %).

Limits of detection were calculated by the DIN 32645 methodology (equivalent to ISO 11843) using calibration straight lines. The calculation was carried out following previous descriptions [31] and implemented through chemCal package [32] of the statistical software R [29].

The methodology has been externally validated by participation in several rounds of the German External Quality Assessment Scheme (GEQUAS), which includes PNP and TCPY (organophosphate metabolites), 3PBA and 4F3PBA (pyrethroid metabolites) and the recently added 6CINA (a neonicotinoid metabolite).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Method optimization

Preliminary MS/MS optimization experiments were carried out using single-compound standard solutions (800 ng/mL) prepared in ACN, to obtain the precursor and product ions. The preliminary collision energy value for each MS transition was obtained by checking the best signal from 10 to 60 eV with an increment of 10 eV. When the collision energy value was selected, the optimal cone voltage value was obtained from the best production transition signal achieved in the range of preliminary collision energy value with an increment of 5 eV. For each

Table 3

Results obtained for 6CINA in the analysis of proficiency testing materials from the G-Equas program. Reference values and tolerance ranges provided by G-Equas are also shown. Concentration units are expressed in ng/mL.

	RV-65		RV-72	
	Sample A	Sample B	Sample A	Sample B
Laboratory result	1.16	3.16	0.95	2.55
Reference result	1.26	2.64	1.01	2.67
Acceptable range	0.84 – 1.68	1.89 – 3.39	0.68 – 1.34	2.04 – 3.30

analyte, two selected reaction monitoring (SRM) were selected, the first most abundant for quantification (Q-SRM) and the second selected for confirmation (C-SRM). SRM transitions, together with their ion ratios (IRs) were used to identify the analytes in the samples and to discriminate against possible co-elutions. The optimum values of retention time (RT), IRs precursor and product ions, collision and cone energies for the quantitative transition, the MRM windows (MRMw) and the ion mode selected for each analyte (positive or negative) are summarized in Table 1.

3.2. Method validation

Linearity was evaluated using calibration curves. Good linearity was obtained in the range of 0.010–60 ng/mL, with determination coefficients (R^2) ranging from 0.9915 to 0.9999 for all the target analytes (Table 2). Sensitivity of the method was assessed by the limit of detection, which were in the range of 0.012 ng/mL and 0.058 ng/mL (Table 2). These values demonstrates an adequate sensitivity for trace analysis of pesticides in human urine.

Accuracy and precision of the method were expressed as recoveries and CVs, respectively. As shown in Table 2, the absolute recoveries of the target analytes ranged from 78 % to 99 %, depending on the compound. Intra-day and inter-day CVs were below 25 % in all the cases, except for OH-TEB, for which a percentage of 26 % was calculated (in the case of QCH inter-day CV). Together with OH-TEB, THPI and 3OH-CARBO were the analytes with the highest CVs. In general, recoveries and CVs were within the acceptable variability limits, indicating that the accuracy and precision of the method were satisfactory for a routine human biomonitoring purposes.

Table 3 shows the laboratory and reference results of 6CINA, a metabolite of IMI and ACE included in the G-EQUAS reference materials. In all the samples analysed from the two G-EQUAS rounds (RV-65 and

RV-72), the levels determined were in accordance with the reference result and their acceptable ranges (Table 3).

Fig. 2 shows the chromatograms of the optimized compounds in a synthetic urine extract (top panel) and the analytes found in a real urine extract (bottom panel). Matrix effects between synthetic urine and real urine extracts were minimized by the use of isotopically labelled standards.

3.3. Strengths and limitations

Compared with the literature, our multitarget method was able to simultaneously detect as many as 5 categories of pesticides and a total of 23 analytes in human urine. In some cases, including NEOs, CBMs and TRs, both the parent pesticide and the metabolite(s) were included in the analysis (Table 1). HPLC-MS/MS instrumentation has been proved to be an optimal and sensitive method for the analysis of pesticide residues in human urine. Although there are some methods that have been able to determine >100 residues in human urine, those usually need to proceed with both liquid and gas chromatography techniques [33]. Matrix effects calculations showed a signal suppression for most of the compounds. These effects might be mediated due to the different physical-chemical properties of the studied compounds, though it is minimized by the use of isotopically-labelled internal standards [20]. In fact, the use of isotopically-labelled standards is also an asset in terms of trueness and precision. In the optimized method, urine volumes remained the same as in the previous method, using a total of 1 mL. Although several studies are able to use lower sample volumes of urine (500 μ L or even less, 200 μ L), this human matrix is usually available at large volumes and involves little discomfort to provide it [34]. Therefore, for certain compounds rarely found or with higher detection limits, this volume might allow a better quantification. And finally, the method has been proved to be an asset in terms of sample throughput, allowing to analyse up to 100 urine samples/week, hence easing the participation in birth cohorts/population studies.

4. Conclusions

A fast and sensitive method for the simultaneous determination of 23 pesticides and their metabolites has been optimized and satisfactorily validated regarding linearity, limits of detection, accuracy and precision. The method is able to analyse up to 5 categories of pesticides, encompassing neonicotinoids, carbamates/thiocarbamates, triazoles, organophosphates and pyrethroids with current or past use. This

Fig. 2. Chromatograms of a spiked synthetic urine extract (QCH) and a real urine extract.

proposed method can be applied as a human biomonitoring tool in large population surveys for human health risk assessment.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Carolina M. Bustamante: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Natalia Bravo:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Paula Ruiz:** Software, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Joan O. Grimalt:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Mercè Garí:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

To facilitate reproducibility and reuse, the code used to perform the method validation and optimization has been made available on GitHub. https://github.com/mercegarí/Pesticides_MethodValidation.

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Supplementary materials

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